

Exploring the Dimensions of Suicidal Ideation: A Comprehensive Review

Rúben Baptista

ABSTRACT

Suicidal ideation is a complex and distressing phenomenon that affects individuals worldwide, with significant repercussions not only for those who experience it but also for their families, communities, and society as a whole. This article thoroughly explores various aspects of suicidal ideation, from its definition and characteristics to its risk factors, assessment methods, intervention, and prevention. It emphasizes the importance of early assessment and diagnosis in identifying individuals at risk, as well as the implementation of evidence-based interventions such as Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT), Interpersonal Therapy (IPT), and Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT). Furthermore, it highlights the need for a multifaceted approach to prevention, including primary, secondary, and tertiary strategies, as well as policies aimed at reducing access to lethal means of suicide. By fostering awareness, strengthening support systems, and ensuring access to quality mental health services, we can make significant strides in preventing and treating suicidal ideation, ultimately offering hope and support to those in need.

Keywords: Suicidal ideation, risk factors, prevalence, consequences, intervention, prevention

Introduction

Suicidal ideation is an extremely serious phenomenon that impacts not only the individuals who experience it, but also their families, communities, and the society in which they are embedded. It encompasses a range of thoughts, plans, or desires to end one's own life, varying in intensity and frequency, from fleeting thoughts to a persistent obsession with death. It is essential to differentiate between passive and active suicidal ideation, as in the former, thoughts are vague or indirect, while in the latter, there is a concrete plan to carry out the act.

The relevance of this topic transcends the individual realm, becoming a concern of global public health magnitude. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 800,000 people lose their lives to suicide annually, making it one of the leading causes of mortality worldwide. For every completed suicide, there are numerous attempts that may result in serious injury or death, underscoring the urgency to understand and address suicidal ideation seriously and compassionately.

In this context, this article aims to explore the various aspects of suicidal ideation, from its risk factors to its consequences, assessment methods, and intervention. In doing so, it seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of this complex phenomenon and provide valuable insights for professionals and individuals involved in the prevention and treatment of suicidal ideation.

Characteristics of Suicidal Ideation

Suicidal ideation is a complex phenomenon that encompasses a variety of thoughts and feelings related to death and self-destruction (Klonsky et al., 2016). In this section, we will explore in detail what constitutes suicidal ideation, its different aspects, and how it can manifest.

Suicidal ideation can be defined as any thought, desire, or planning related to ending one's own life (American Psychiatric Association [APA], 2013). These thoughts vary in intensity, duration, and specificity, ranging from vague

and transient thoughts to detailed and persistent plans for suicide.

There are two main types of suicidal ideation: passive and active.

Passive suicidal ideation refers to vague thoughts or desires about dying, without a specific plan for suicide. For example, a person may think that it would be better if they were dead or that everything would be easier if they didn't exist (Hawton & van Heeringen, 2009). On the other hand, active suicidal ideation involves specific thoughts and plans for suicide, including considerations of how, when, and where to commit the act. For instance, someone may elaborate a detailed plan to intentionally overdose on medication, hang themselves, among other methods (APA, 2013).

Suicidal ideation can arise from a variety of factors, which vary from individual to individual. Some of the factors that may contribute to the development of suicidal ideation include: mental disorders, as suicidal ideation is associated with conditions such as depression, bipolar disorder, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), among others (Klonsky et al., 2016); traumatic experiences, such as abuse, loss of loved ones, bullying, or failure to achieve important goals, can trigger suicidal thoughts (Hawton & van Heeringen, 2009); environmental factors, such as easy access to lethal means (such as knives, poisons, medications, etc.), unemployment, social isolation, or lack of emotional support (Klonsky et al., 2016).

Prevalence of Suicidal Ideation

According to data from the World Health Organization (WHO), suicidal ideation is a significant public health issue worldwide (WHO, 2021). It is estimated that millions of people across all continents have suicidal thoughts at some point in their lives, with significant variations depending on the country, region, and demographic group.

Different population groups may exhibit higher vulnerability to suicidal ideation. Some of the demographic factors that may influence the prevalence of suicidal ideation include: age, as

adolescents and young adults are more likely to report suicidal ideation compared to other age groups (Kessler et al., 2005); gender, as despite higher rates of completed suicide in men, women tend to report suicidal ideation more frequently (Nock et al., 2008); socioeconomic status, as individuals in socioeconomically vulnerable situations, such as unemployment, poverty, or lack of access to mental health services, may be at higher risk of suicidal ideation (Lorant et al., 2005).

In addition to demographic factors, there are specific groups that may be at higher risk of suicidal ideation due to particular circumstances. These may include individuals suffering from mental disorders, such as depression, bipolar disorder, or schizophrenia, as they have an increased likelihood of experiencing suicidal ideation (Borges et al., 2010); people who have been victims of physical, sexual, or emotional abuse, or who have experienced significant traumas, may have an increased risk of suicidal ideation (Joiner, 2005); and military veterans who have faced combat or traumatic experiences during service may be at higher risk of suicidal ideation due to combat stress and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) (Bryan et al., 2016).

Risk and Protective Factors

Risk factors are characteristics or circumstances that increase a person's vulnerability to suicidal ideation (Franklin et al., 2017). Some of the most common risk factors include: mental disorders (Franklin et al., 2017); individuals with close family members who have committed suicide may have an increased risk of suicidal ideation due to genetic, environmental, or familial factors (Brent et al., 2002); traumatic experiences (Klonsky et al., 2016); lack of social support or meaningful connections with others which can increase feelings of hopelessness and loneliness (Van Orden et al., 2010); and easy access to lethal suicide methods (Hawton et al., 2013). Protective factors are resources or characteristics that can help reduce the risk of

suicidal ideation and promote mental well-being. Some of the protective factors include: positive relationships with friends, family, coworkers, or community members, as they can provide emotional support and reduce social isolation (Klonsky et al., 2016); access to quality psychological and psychiatric treatment, as it can help identify and treat underlying mental health issues (Franklin et al., 2017); development of healthy coping strategies, such as problem-solving, effective communication, and stress management, as it can strengthen emotional resilience (Van Orden et al., 2010); having meaningful goals, personal interests, and a sense of purpose in life that can increase hope and motivation to face challenges (Klonsky et al., 2016); and implementation of policies that restrict access to lethal suicide methods, such as gun control laws or secure packaging of medications, can reduce the suicide rate (Hawton et al., 2013).

Consequences of Suicidal Ideation

Suicidal ideation is closely linked to a range of mental disorders (Franklin et al., 2017; Klonsky et al., 2016). This condition can cause intense psychological suffering, leading to feelings of hopelessness, helplessness, and emotional isolation. Additionally, the constant presence of suicidal thoughts can interfere with the individual's ability to function, impacting their daily life and potentially affecting their quality of life.

Suicidal ideation can place significant strain on the individual's interpersonal relationships, especially with friends, family, and intimate partners (Joiner et al., 2009; Klonsky et al., 2016). Those close to someone with suicidal ideation may experience episodes of stress, worry, and feelings of helplessness while trying to offer support and assistance. This can lead to conflicts, misunderstandings, and feelings of distance in relationships.

Although suicidal ideation itself is not suicidal behavior, it is associated with an increased risk of suicide attempts and completed suicide (Nock et al., 2008; Franklin et al., 2017). The presence of suicidal ideation indicates profound

emotional distress and a desire to escape psychological suffering, which can lead to self-destructive behaviors if not properly addressed. The persistence of suicidal ideation can negatively impact all aspects of an individual's life, including their work, education, relationships, and leisure activities. The constant state of emotional distress and the struggle against suicidal thoughts can result in a decline in quality of life and a sense of hopelessness about the future.

Assessment and Diagnosis of Suicidal Ideation

The assessment of suicidal ideation typically begins with a detailed interview conducted by a trained mental health professional (Joiner et al., 2009). During this interview, the professional may explore the following aspects: the clinical history, which includes an investigation of the individual's medical and psychiatric history, including past experiences of suicidal ideation, suicide attempts, mental disorders, and traumatic events; exploration of current symptoms of depression, anxiety, hopelessness, helplessness, and other risk factors associated with suicidal ideation; determining the level of risk for imminent suicidal behavior, including the presence of a specific plan, access to lethal means, and available protective factors; and assessing the presence and quality of the individual's social support, including family connections, friendships, and access to community resources.

In addition to the clinical interview, mental health professionals may use a variety of standardized instruments to assess suicidal ideation (Nock et al., 2008). Some commonly used assessment instruments include: suicidal ideation assessment scales, such as the Beck Scale for Suicide Ideation (BSI) (Beck et al., 1979) or the Columbia-Suicide Severity Rating Scale (C-SSRS) (Posner et al., 2011), which can help quantify the severity of suicidal ideation and identify associated risk factors; and Mental Disorder Screening Questionnaires such as the PHQ-9 (Patient Health Questionnaire - 9) or the BDI-II (Beck

Depression Inventory - Second Edition) which can be used to assess the presence and severity of depression symptoms and other mental disorders.

It is important to differentiate between suicidal ideation and other intrusive thoughts or concerns related to mental health (Franklin et al., 2017). Differential diagnosis can help identify the specific needs of the individual and guide appropriate treatment planning.

Intervention and Treatment of Suicidal Ideation

Several models can be used for the intervention and treatment of suicidal ideation, including:

Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT): Widely used in treating suicidal ideation (Hawton et al., 2013), CBT focuses on identifying and modifying negative and distorted thought patterns, promoting healthy coping skills, and strengthening emotional resilience.

Interpersonal Therapy (IPT): Concentrates on improving interpersonal relationships and resolving conflicts to reduce emotional distress and strengthen the individual's social support (Joiner et al., 2009).

Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT): Emphasizes acceptance of difficult thoughts and emotions while promoting the identification of personal values and meaningful life goals (Linehan et al., 2015).

It's recommended to use helpline services that offer immediate and confidential emotional support for individuals in crisis (Gould et al., 2007). However, emergency intervention may be necessary when situations of imminent suicide risk occur, including psychiatric hospitalization or intervention by specialized mental health crisis teams (Hawton et al., 2016).

Working with a multidisciplinary team involving psychiatrists, psychologists, social workers, nurses, and other mental health professionals is essential to ensure that the treatment plan is comprehensive and tailored to the individual's needs (Mann et al., 2005). Care coordination among members of the mental

health team is critical for the success of the intervention (Mann et al., 2016).

A personalized safety protocol should be developed with specific strategies for managing crises and warning signs to prevent relapses and future suicidal behaviors (Stanley & Brown, 2012). Regular follow-up with mental health professionals is essential. Participation in support groups is also crucial for maintaining emotional stability and providing ongoing support over time (Hawton et al., 2008).

Prevention of Suicidal Ideation

For the prevention of suicidal ideation, the use of primary, secondary, and tertiary prevention strategies is recommended.

- **Primary prevention strategies involve:**

Raising awareness about warning signs of suicidal ideation and providing information about mental health resources and healthy coping strategies can help reduce stigma surrounding suicide and encourage people to seek help when needed (World Health Organization, 2014).

Encouraging healthy lifestyles, including a balanced diet, regular exercise, adequate sleep, and stress management techniques, can strengthen emotional resilience and reduce the risk of developing mental health problems (Mental Health Foundation, 2020).

- **Secondary prevention strategies include:**

Implementing risk screening programs in clinical, school, and community settings can help identify individuals at risk of suicidal ideation early and direct them to appropriate interventions (American Academy of Pediatrics, 2016).

Offering mental health first aid training for healthcare professionals, educators, community leaders, and members of the general public can increase awareness about suicide and empower

people to offer effective support to individuals in crisis (Kitchener & Jorm, 2008).

- **Tertiary prevention strategies involve:**

Providing follow-up interventions and intensive support after a suicide attempt or mental health crisis can help minimize the risk of recurrence and promote long-term recovery (Hawton & van Heeringen, 2009).

Ensuring continued access to quality mental health services and promoting a strong social support network can help protect vulnerable individuals against relapses and future episodes of suicidal ideation (World Health Organization, 2014).

Implementing policies and interventions that limit access to lethal suicide methods, such as firearms, pesticides, and medications, can significantly reduce the suicide rate in a community or population (Mann et al., 2005). Promoting the use of secure medication packaging, which reduces the risk of accidental or intentional overdose, can help prevent deaths from drug poisoning (World Health Organization, 2017).

Conclusion

Suicidal ideation is a complex and distressing phenomenon that affects individuals worldwide, with significant repercussions not only for those who experience it but also for their families, communities, and society at large. This article has thoroughly explored various aspects of suicidal ideation, from its definition and characteristics to its risk factors, assessment methods, intervention, and prevention.

It is crucial to recognize that suicidal ideation does not arise in isolation but is often associated with underlying mental health conditions, traumatic experiences, and environmental stressors. Therefore, effectively addressing suicidal ideation requires a comprehensive

understanding of its roots and individual contexts.

Early assessment and diagnosis play a crucial role in early identification and intervention, allowing timely access to therapeutic and supportive interventions. Implementing evidence-based treatments such as Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT), Interpersonal Therapy (IPT), and Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) offer hope and resources for those struggling with suicidal ideation.

Furthermore, preventing suicidal ideation requires a multifaceted approach, involving primary, secondary, and tertiary prevention strategies, as well as policies aimed at reducing access to lethal means of suicide. By promoting awareness, strengthening social support systems, and ensuring access to quality mental health services, we can work to mitigate the devastating impact of suicidal ideation in our communities.

At the heart of all these efforts is a commitment to offering support, compassion, and hope to those facing the daily struggle with suicidal ideation. By working together as healthcare professionals, communities, and society at large, we can make significant progress in preventing and treating this serious public health issue, providing a path to recovery and emotional well-being for all individuals.

References

American Academy of Pediatrics. (2016). *Suicide risk and prevention: The role of pediatricians*. *Pediatrics*, 138(1), e20161512. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2016-1512>

American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders* (5th ed.). <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.books.9780890425596>

Borges, G., Nock, M. K., Haro Abad, J. M., Hwang, I., Sampson, N. A., Alonso, J., ... & Kessler, R. C. (2010). *Twelve-month*

prevalence of and risk factors for suicide attempts in the World Health Organization World Mental Health Surveys. *The Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, 71(12), 1617–1628. <https://doi.org/10.4088/jcp.08m04967blu>

Brent, D. A., Bridge, J., Johnson, B. A., & Connolly, J. (2002). *Suicidal behavior runs in families: A controlled family study of adolescent suicide victims*. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 59(8), 741–749. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archpsyc.59.8.741>

Franklin, J. C., Ribeiro, J. D., Fox, K. R., Bentley, K. H., Kleiman, E. M., Huang, X., ... & Nock, M. K. (2017). *Risk factors for suicidal thoughts and behaviors: A meta-analysis of 50 years of research*. *Psychological Bulletin*, 143(2), 187–232. <https://doi.org/10.1037/bul0000084>

Gould, M. S., Kalafat, J., HarrisMunfakh, J. L., & Kleinman, M. (2007). *An evaluation of crisis hotline outcomes. Part 1: Nonsuicidal crisis callers*. *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 37(3), 322–337.

Hawton, K., & van Heeringen, K. (2009). *Suicide*. *The Lancet*, 373(9672), 1372–1381. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(09\)60372-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(09)60372-x)

Hawton, K., Saunders, K. E. A., & O'Connor, R. C. (2013). *Self-harm and suicide in adolescents*. *The Lancet*, 379(9834), 2373–2382. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(12\)60322-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(12)60322-5)

Hawton, K., Witt, K. G., Salisbury, T. L., Arensman, E., Gunnell, D., Hazell, P., ... & van Heeringen, K. (2016). *Psychosocial interventions for self-harm in adults*. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, (5), CD012189.

Hawton, K., Witt, K. G., Taylor Salisbury, T. L., Arensman, E., Gunnell, D., Hazell, P., ... & van Heeringen, K. (2015). *Interventions for*

self-harm in children and adolescents. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, (12), CD012013.

Joiner, T. E. (2005). *Why people die by suicide*. Harvard University Press.

Joiner, T. E., Van Orden, K. A., Witte, T. K., Rudd, M. D., & Joiner, M. L. (2009). *The interpersonal theory of suicide: Guidance for working with suicidal clients*. American Psychological Association.

Kessler, R. C., Borges, G., & Walters, E. E. (2005). Prevalence of and risk factors for lifetime suicide attempts in the National Comorbidity Survey. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 62(6), 617–626. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archpsyc.62.6.617>

Kitchener, B. A., & Jorm, A. F. (2008). Mental health first aid training for the public: evaluation of effects on knowledge, attitudes and helping behavior. *BMC Psychiatry*, 8(1), 8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-244X-8-8>

Klonsky, E. D., May, A. M., & Saffer, B. Y. (2016). Suicide, suicide attempts, and suicidal ideation. *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology*, 12, 307–330. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-clinpsy-021815-093204>

Linehan, M. M., Korslund, K. E., Harned, M. S., Gallop, R. J., Lungu, A., Linehan, M. M., Korslund, K. E., Harned, M. S., Gallop, R. J., Lungu, A., Neacsiu, A. D., ... & Murray-Gregory, A. M. (2015). Dialectical behavior therapy for high suicide risk in individuals with borderline personality disorder: A randomized clinical trial and component analysis. *JAMA Psychiatry*, 72(5), 475–482.

Lorant, V., Kunst, A. E., Huisman, M., Costa, G., Mackenbach, J., & EU Working Group on Socioeconomic Inequalities in Health. (2005). *Socio-economic inequalities in suicide: A European comparative study*. *The British*

Journal of Psychiatry, 187(1), 49–54. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.187.1.49>

Mann, J. J., Apter, A., Bertolote, J., Beautrais, A., Currier, D., Haas, A., ... & Hendin, H. (2005). Suicide prevention strategies: a systematic review. *JAMA*, 294(16), 2064–2074. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.294.16.2064>

Mental Health Foundation. (2020). *How to look after your mental health*. <https://www.mentalhealth.org.uk/publications/how-to-mental-health>

Nock, M. K., Borges, G., Bromet, E. J., Alonso, J., Angermeyer, M., Beautrais, A., ... & Williams, D. (2008). Cross-national prevalence and risk factors for suicidal ideation, plans, and attempts. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 192(2), 98–105. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.bp.107.040113>

Organização Mundial da Saúde. (2021). *Suicide*. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/suicide>

Posner, K., Brown, G. K., Stanley, B., Brent, D. A., Yershova, K. V., Oquendo, M. A., ... & Mann, J. J. (2011). *The Columbia–Suicide Severity Rating Scale*